

Adoption of Evidence-Based Medicine: A Comparative Study of Hospital and Community Pharmacists in Saudi Arabia

Questionnaire

Section 1: informed consent.

Please remember that your participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw from the study at any time for any reason. The study will include pharmacists from hospitals and community pharmacies working in Medina. By clicking I agree below you're indicating that you're working as a pharmacist in the Madinah and agreeing to participate in this study.

Section 2:

Socio-demographic characteristics

1. **Age:**
2. **Gender**
 - a) Male
 - b) Female
3. **Practice setting:**
 - a) Community pharmacy
 - b) Hospital Pharmacy
4. **Highest professional/academic degree**
 - a) BSc. Pharm
 - b) Pharm.D
 - c) MS. Pharm

d) Ph.D

5. Country of Graduation

- a) Saudi Arabia
- b) Middle East
- c) North America
- d) Europe
- e) Africa
- f) Other:

6. Years of experience

- a) < 1 Years
- b) 1–5 Years
- c) 5–10 Years
- d) > 10 Years

7. Previously undergone any training courses in Evidence-based medicine (EBM)

- a) Yes
- b) No**

Section 3: Knowledge of evidence-based medicine

	Statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	EBM involves the process of critically appraising research findings as the bases for making the best clinical decision.					
2	EBM focuses on the best current available research without considering clinical experience.					
3	Patients' preferences should be prioritized over clinicians' preferences in					

	making clinical decisions.					
4	EBM improves clinicians' understanding of research methodology.					
5	EBM can be practiced in situations where there is doubt about any aspect of clinical management.					
6	The increasing number of systematic reviews that are applicable to general practice can be found in the Cochrane Library.					
7	Difficulty in understanding statistical terms is the major setback in applying evidence-based medicine.					

Section 4: Attitude on evidence-based medicine

	Statements	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	I believe that EBM is a threat to good clinical practice.					
2	I believe practicing EBM can improve patient health outcomes.					
3	I am willing to learn/practice EBM if given the opportunity.					
4	I feel that research findings are very important in my day-to-day management of patients.					
5	I believe that years of experience is more valuable than EBM.					
6	I am convinced that applying EBM in practice increases the effectiveness of my work.					
7	I am certain that understanding the basic mechanisms of disease					

	is sufficient for good clinical practice.					
8	I feel that access to databases is vital in obtaining journals on EBM.					
9	I feel that reading the conclusions of a systematic review is adequate for clinical practice.					
10	I feel that practicing EBM would produce better health practitioners.					
11	I think it is mandatory for pharmacists to continuously update their knowledge/education about EBM to deliver efficient patient care.					

Section 5: Practice of evidence-based medicine

	Statements	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1	I apply EBM in practice.					
2	I use multiple search engines for systematic review.					
3	I do not have enough time to study/practice EBM.					
4	I join continuous medical education for an update regarding EBM.					
5	I promote and share knowledge about EBM with my colleagues at the workplace.					

6	I usually translate a clinical question into a form that can be answered from the literature (PICO).					
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Section 6: Technical terms

	Items	It would not be helpful to me to	I don't understand it but wants to	Some understanding	Yes, understood and I could
1	Relative risk				
2	Absolute risk				
3	Systematic review				
4	Odds ratio				
5	Meta-analysis				
6	Clinical effectiveness				
7	Confidence interval				
8	Number needed to treat				
9	Heterogeneity				

10	Types of errors				
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